

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN HISTORY LESSONS AND THEIR PLACE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the use of innovative technologies in history lessons, the need to use them in the modern education system, as well as the impact on the effectiveness of the educational process and students' cognitive interest in science

In the context of educational reforms, innovative activities aimed at introducing various pedagogical innovations in higher education gained special importance.

Innovations in teaching are new methods and new methods of organizing the content of education, a method used by the teacher to increase the effective work of students in the educational process.

Today, education must meet the demands of the modern world. It is the innovative methods in teaching that must be aimed at the future life of a person, and in higher education, at the preparation of a highly educated specialist. Many students who come to the institution are not so interested in science as history. Therefore, the teacher's goal is to make them interested in science. Since the youth of the 21st century are people of the information age, in the process of working with them, it is necessary to develop their ability to independently and motivationally organize cognitive activity, to use the elements of causal and structural-functional analysis, thus to identify the important features of the studied object, should be encouraged to independently choose criteria for comparison, analysis.

To implement these tasks, the history teacher will be effective if he uses innovative educational technologies.

Passive, active and interactive strategies are distinguished in modern teaching. A skillful combination of these strategies ensures the effectiveness of teaching and the quality of education.

Information and communication technologies enable the development of independent, research and creative work skills, contribute to self-expression and personal development. Students show very good results when using them - they make presentations. The introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process made it possible to increase the visibility and emotional component of learning, conducting virtual tours to museums, etc.

In our opinion, the use of modern information technologies increased the activity of students in the lesson, enabled the effective organization of students' knowledge and research activities, increased the expressiveness and emotional content of the lesson, and all this contributed to the development of students' creative qualities and their self-awareness. It helps to understand. Interactive educational technologies are considered as a method of acquiring knowledge and developing skills in the process of relations and interactions between the teacher and the student as subjects of educational activity. Interactive activities in the audience include the organization and development of dialogic communication, which leads to mutual understanding, interaction and joint solving of common but important tasks for each participant. Teacher in interactive educational technologies:

and the **student:**

Instead of an
object of
influence

also the role of information: information is not a goal, but a means of mastering actions and operations will change significantly. The introduction of such training helps to organize cognitive, practical and creative activities.

Thanks to interactive learning, almost all students are involved in the learning process. They have the ability to understand and reason about what they know and think. Each person makes a unique individual contribution to the process of sharing knowledge, ideas and ways of doing things. In addition, it happens in an atmosphere of goodwill and mutual support, which not only allows for the acquisition of new knowledge, but also develops the cognitive activity itself, transferring it to higher forms of cooperation.

One of the important modern educational technologies is the technology of developing critical thinking, that is, thinking that refutes established ideas and projects new ideas based on one's own experience. This technology is based on:

As a result of applying the technology of development of critical thinking, we can note the following:

- ❖ high motivation of students to study;
- ❖ improvement of thinking process and flexibility of thinking;
- ❖ work with independently structured concepts;
- ❖ confirm or reject the point of view of another person;
- ❖ analysis of received data.

One of the technologies that provides student-oriented education is the project method, which develops creativity, cognitive activity and independence. I consider the project and research activities on the acquisition of operational knowledge in the process of socialization of students to be promising. During the implementation of the project, students synthesize knowledge

during their research, combine information from related disciplines, search for more effective ways to solve project problems, and communicate with each other. Collaborative activities really demonstrate the wide range of possibilities of cooperation, in which students set goals, determine the optimal means of achieving them, distribute responsibilities, fully demonstrate individual competence.

For a certain period of time, students solve cognitive, research or other problems. Several educational projects have been implemented recently. Among them are "In New Uzbekistan - modern methods of studying history", "Study of the latest history of Uzbekistan", "Followers of Tomaris", "Amir Temur's place and role in history" and others.

In the study of history, group study of various educational materials, followed by presentation and discussion, is used to develop students' independence and creative activity, as well as to develop teamwork skills. Within each group, the activities are distributed among the participants of the project according to the capabilities and inclinations of each of them, for example, when the following topics are covered: "Leading political parties of Uzbekistan", "Combat actions of Uzbek soldiers on the fronts during the Great Patriotic War". Thus, in the example of the above topics, sheets with tasks are prepared for each group, they will then perform these tasks and prepare a presentation on the results of the work performed.

Taking into account the complexity of the studied material, modular technology elements are sometimes used, which is based on the fact that each lesson should help to learn new information and to form the skills and competencies of processing this information. Lectures (lessons for learning new material), seminars, research, practical work, tests (lessons for taking into account and evaluating knowledge and skills) are organized.

In conclusion, it should be said that the use of ICT, Internet resources, innovative technologies, interactive methods in the teaching of history in higher education not only improves students' knowledge and skills in working with additional materials, but also strengthens the material. helps, increases efficiency, as well as help to improve the qualifications and professional skills of the teacher, to conduct lessons based on the requirements of the time, to make them interesting, to get acquainted with the latest achievements of science and the methodology of teaching history will give. Systematic work on the use of modern pedagogical technologies and their elements in the educational process leads to an increase in the indicators of history in groups, students actively participate in classes, participate in science Olympiads, scientific-practical conferences.

References:

1. Salieva, Z. Z. (2018). Reading comprehension and comprehension strategies. *Учёный XXI века. Международный научный журнал*, (7-1), 42.
2. Salieva, Z. Z. (2024). DISTRACTERS OF MOTIVATION IN PRODUCING A WRITTEN TEXT OF STUDENTS IN EFL CLASSROOM. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 3(4 SPECIAL), 599-602.
3. Salieva, Z. (2023). SOME CHALLENGES FACED BY EFL STUDENTS ON WRITING SKILL. *UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH*, 1(7), 69-75.
4. Салиева, З. З. (2023). YOZISHNI ORQITISHNING XUSUSIYATLARI VA YONDASHUVLARI. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 6(3).

5. Гулрух, С. (2022). ВО 'LAJAK BOSH LANG 'ICH SINF O 'QITUVCHILARINI IJODIY FAOLIYATNI TASHKIL ETISHGA TAYYORLASH PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA: Saidova Gulruh Halim qizi, Nizomiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti. *Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал*, (1), 208-214.
6. Qizi, S. G. H., & Qizi, H. H. H. (2023). TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING "4K" KOMPETENSIYALARI: KREATIVLIK, TANQIDIY FIKRLASH, KOMMUNIKATSIYA, KOOPERATSIYA. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 12), 430-432.
7. Saidova, G. (2020). CREATIVE CLASSES AS A MEANS OF FORMING PERSONAL AND COMPETENCY-BASED QUALITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PRIMARY CLASSES. In *ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ* (pp. 20-23).
8. Saidova, G. (2020). ORGANIZATIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF THE TEACHER OF PRIMARY CLASSROOM IN THE PERIOD OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 86-90).
9. Gulchexra, K. (2023). FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(03), 40-44.
10. Кахарова, Д. С. БЎЛАЖАК ЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER Саидова Гулрух Халим қизи.
11. Ostonovich, B. O., & Khudayberdievich, S. H. (2023). Linguistic Analysis of Knowledge Issues in Psychological Discourse. *Journal of Science-Innovative Research in Uzbekistan*, 1(5), 355-369.
12. Bobokalonov, O. (2023). FRENCH SHIFONEMAS IN PHRASEOLOGICAL CONSTRUCTION ON HISTORICAL SOURCES. *АКТА NUUz (O'zMU Xabarlari)*.
13. Bobokalonov, O. (2023). Les phytophraséologismes ou phytophrasèmes. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 31(31).
14. Aripova, S. (2024). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 98-101.
15. Tohirovna, A. S. (2023). ENHANCING INDEPENDENT LEARNING STRATEGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH CASE STUDIES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(11), 651-652.
16. Aripova, S. T. (2023). INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA TALABALARNING IJODIY MUSTAQILLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISH. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 259-263.
17. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 7(1), 118-123.

18. Taxirovna, A. S. (2023). Lingua-cultural aspects of the translation of English and Uzbek stories. *Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany)*, 536-540.
19. Aripova, S. (2023). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS. *Science and innovation*, 2(C12), 37-42.
20. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS, SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI.
21. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2024). Objective Factors Affecting Uzbekistan's Access To The Bologna Agreement. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 29, 16-19.
22. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2024). THE INFLUENCE OF THE BOLOGNA PROCESS ON YOUTH'S WORLDVIEW. *Confrencea*, 1(1), 270-274.
23. kizi Abdurakhimova, T. A. (2023). Issues of Spiritual and Moral Education of the Mature Generation in Independent Uzbekistan. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(3S), 3864-3873.
24. Moydinova, E. (2021). THE ROLE OF MODERN ENGLISH TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGE OF DIGITALIZATION. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
25. Moydinova, E. (2022). INGLIZ TILINI O 'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
26. Moydinova, E. (2022). UNIVERSAL MASOFAVIY TA'LIM SHAROITIDA VEB-KVEST TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISHNING SAMARADORLIGI. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
27. Odinaxon, I. (2023). TURLI TIZIMLI TILLARDA TARJIMON MAHORATI. *UNIVERSAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE*, 1(4), 27-32.
28. Ismanova, O. (2023). NEMIS VA OZBEK TILLAR KESIMIDA TARJIMONNING TARJIMADA LEKSIK SINONIMLARDAN TANLAB FOYDALANISH USLUBLARI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11 Part 2), 157-160.
29. Axrorova, R. U., Urunbayevna, I. O., & Ibrohimjon ogli, Q. A. (2022). XORIJIY TILLARNI OQITISHDA HAR BIR OQUVCHI BILAN INDIVIDUAL SHUGULLANISH VA KOPRIK TIL MOHIYATI. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(12), 22-24.
30. Kenjabaev, Ж. (2022). The implementation of literature in teaching speaking for advanced students. *Общество и инновации*, 3(2/S), 262-265.
31. Kenjabaev, J. A. (2022). METHODS THROUGH THE INTERNET IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. *Экономика и социум*, (12-2 (103)), 67-70.
32. Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). Communicative Language Teaching And The System Of Exercises. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 1017-1022.

- 33.** Кенжабаев, Ж. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ЭТАП РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ О ЯЗЫКЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (2 (105)), 704-707.
- 34.** Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH THROUGH INTERNET SITES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 3(11), 59-71.
- 35.** Kenjabayev, J. A. Linguistic features of the development of oral speech competence of students of the direction of physical culture education (on the example of sports terminology). *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences.-UK*, 11, 48-51.
- 36.** Abdusalimovich, K. J. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH THROUGH INTERNET SITES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 3(11), 59-71.
- 37.** Кенжабаев, Д. (2023). METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING ENGLISH BASED ON INTERNET RESOURCES. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(11).
- 38.** Kenjabayev, J. A. (2024). Modern Teaching Methods in Teaching English. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 3(1), 52-56.

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